

Industry 5.0 interventions: towards an approach for behavioral Teaching Factories

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Introduction

In Industry 5.0, a company's perspective (i.e. values) shapes how it integrates the Industry 5.0 concept in their daily operation. Some companies may prioritize eco-friendly production, while others may seek a balance between AI and human creativity [1]. This perspective influences the adoption of technologies, practices and work systems [2]. Ultimately, Industry 5.0 should allow each company to tailor innovation to its unique goals. To achieve this transformation, interventions must be performed, exploiting relevant design [3] and evaluation [4].

As such, the current work pursues a two-fold research objective:

- investigating soft interventions (where not all pillars are part of the incentive or no specific skills have been targeted)
 - framing soft interventions as a Complex Adaptive System [5], one can highlight flexibility and context-specific solutions.
- considering the behavioral Teaching Factory, engaging both transformative learning [6] and problem solving (a form of Teaching Factory [7]).

Methodology

The procedure, was similar in all cases, as per Table 1.

Table 1: Generic description of interventions

Stage	Description
1	Identification of internal incentives
2	Exploitation of internal transformation / training procedure / desired outcome
3	Presentation in terms of templates (design [3] and evaluation [4])
4	Running initial questionnaire* at job level
5	Running initial questionnaire* at company level (not always possible)
6	External training with respect to (a) behaviors and (b) problem solving capacity
7	Running final questionnaire* at job level
8	Running final questionnaire* at company level
9	Estimate metrics based on differences in the questionnaires
* The responses are on a Likert 1-5 scale	

Some comments follow:

- Three companies took part
- Companies A and B focused on facilitating decision making through elaboration of digital technologies, with the focus being on human centricity and resilience
- In Company C, Human Centricity and Sustainability were the focus
- Company C had already begun an internal transformation towards green production, hence the step 5 was not possible
- Employees from all companies underwent a brief training, where sessions focused mainly on the behaviors

The questionnaire of the companies (focusing on jobs) can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Heuristic questions in the questionnaire and distribution of pillars.

Major Findings

It can be summarized that interventions in all cases have been successful, with respect to the perspective of upskilling. What is considered as metric is the difference in the responses to the questionnaires (before and after the training sessions), grouped per pillar. Hereafter, some major findings can be seen (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2: Results of upskilling for company A.

Figure 3: Results of upskilling for company C.

Also, it is interesting to see some generalization results. Using the question with the lowest score as a statistical control metric of bias, it is noted, that, i.e. for the case of Company A, it can be concluded for the population (through confidence intervals [8][9]) that the intervention in all three pillars is efficient. Furthermore, it is noted that there is strong and significant correlation between Human Centricity and Sustainability in the case of Company A.

Additionally, company-wise, their final state was also found satisfactory. Figure 4 hereafter summarizes their status after the overall intervention, based on a template questionnaire. Also, Table 2 summarizes some aspects of the evaluation of the intervention.

Figure 4: Results of upskilling for company C, with respect to the three pillars.

Table 2: Questionnaire for Company level – interesting responses

Aspect of Intervention	Responses
Easiness	Neutral to Moderately easy
Generic enough for other trainees	Extremely generic
Easy to extent	Moderately easy
What aspects would you add to such interventions to achieve targets, such as management structure change?	Continuous evaluation
How will the delegation of decision-making affect the existing management structure?	Better and timely data, Managers as trainers
What else would make this intervention successful?	Fast engagement of VETs towards new qualifications

Implications

Apart from the conclusions that Industry 5.0, offering proper perspectives and templates, can be integrated into training (and production), it can be summarized for future interventions that:

- Standardized tests would be case dependent
- The relationship between antecedents and outcomes [10] may be more complex than anticipated, i.e. pillars in general can be considered to be coupled

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